

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SHERIFF****FIRST NAME: MOHAMED****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****MDIACOURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: RP1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete the text to show the actual information below:**

The author uses US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author uses Turabian (in-text/parenthetical citations)

The author uses Zotero to insert references

The author uses Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author uses the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2013 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page numbers in the text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Basic Of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5,11,& 21)
3. Basics Of Proper English Writing (EUCLID 2019, 23-32)
4. Citations (EUCLID 2019, 11-17)
5. Referencing Style (EUCLID 2019, 4-12)
6. The Use Of Footnote And Endnote (EUCLID 2019, 51-53)
7. Use Structure And Logical Flow (EUCLID 2019, 13)

ACADEMIC WRITING: A PAINFUL PROCESS OF MENTAL CASTRATION

1) INTRODUCTION

All over the world, academic writing including research papers, theses, and dissertations is a herculean task for not only non-English speakers but also for native English speakers. There are lots of complexity, difficulty, and challenges associated with academic writing including formatting and citation styles, punctuation and grammar, adherence to intellectual property regulations, lexical difficulties, and methodologies used in data collections. These challenges combined by other factors had threatened meaningful contributions to intellectualism, leading to an unprecedented decline of writers around the world, especially in developing countries.

As a nonnative speaker of English and with little knowledge in computer software and applications, I am writing this Response Paper (RP) with the feelings of trepidation and thrill. First, I had the feeling of trepidation because unlike other online courses and

universities around the world, pursuing a program at EUCLID University is never rosy, soft, and pleasurable. What I thought was supposed to be an ordinary orientation turned out to be a painful intellectual exercise of mental castration. Pursuing EUCLID's programs involves a rigorous academic exercise, including brooding on books, limited socialization, the use of sophisticated software, and computer programing including Zotero, chrome connector, and Turabian styles of referencing. Despite these challenges and threats, I am confronted with, including the task of drafting an RP, the anxiety in me contributed to the drafting of this RP. Most importantly, after carefully reading EUCLID's LMS learning materials and watching the 14-minute video, I was pushed to undertake this exercise by adhering to EUCLID's rules of formatting papers including in-text citations, footnotes, and bibliography. Despite all the challenges, I had it at the back of my mind that, "...good things are difficult to achieve and bad things are very easy to get."

2) THE BASICS OF ESSAY WRITING

In my five years working for the Department of State in Freetown, Sierra Leone, I have been the lead drafter for several reports including the department of State congressional reports such as the *Human Rights Report*, *Child Labor Reports*, *Trafficking in Persons Report*, and the *Inter-Religious Freedom Reports*. Besides these congressional reports, I am also charged with the responsibility of drafting other reports including cables on political and human rights issues in the country. Writing these types of essays (cables and reports) requires focus, accuracy, coherence, and clarity. Most importantly, I try to the best my ability to be extremely balanced, objective, and honest. Besides these emotional and professional qualities, I have ensured that the draft is largely free from grammatical, spelling, punctuation, and other inaccuracies. This aspect brings the intervention of other sections including *Political*, *Public*, *Defense*, *Consular*, *Economics*, and the *USAID sections*. This stage by stage clearing process brings in balanced and objective reporting. The respective heads of sections must clear before being sent to Washington.

The Euclid University MDIA orientation began by introducing me to Dr. Kabiru Gulma as the instructor for the ACA-401 course. I began the ACA-401 course by first watching a 14-minute video. The video essentially explains issues around academic writing including a response paper, major paper, and quiz paper. Furthermore, the introductory video started with the instruction to download and install the Zotero and chrome connector applications or software. I learned that the essence of downloading these software applications was to aid students to do accurate and appropriate citations and referencing at the drafting p stage. Amazingly, as indicated by the video, once I installed the Zotero and Chrome Connector applications, I was able to electronically reference using the Turabian citation style also, I was able to electronically generate reference and bibliography. I recommend that other students, especially those in the social sciences and humanities, use the Zotero and Chrome connector to do their in-text citations and bibliography whenever they are drafting an academic paper because of its usefulness and reliability (EUCLID 2019, 2).

Although the video essentially discussed and recommended the use of Turabian citation styles including the in-text citation, endnote, footnote, and bibliography, it further

briefly talked and recommended to certain students including the medical and legal students, adopt the Chicago, MLA, and APA reference model.

Most importantly, the video further brought to the fore the issue of evidence-based writing as a must in the field of academia. But what constitutes evidence-based writing remains an intellectual polemic. Notwithstanding the diverse views among the intellectual communities, the University of North Carolina stated that evidence-based writing involves the use of data, facts, studies, statistics, or expert opinions from reliable sources to support an idea (<https://www.fluentu.com>). For instance, a proposition that the current global warming trend is of significance because most of it is very likely human-induced and proceeding at a rate that is unprecedented in the past 1,300 years. Using a reliable source, such as the NASA-sponsored site Global Climate Change, can directly support your claim and accord it the legitimacy and trust it deserves. This reinforces the fundamental reasons for referencing in the field of academia and professional circle.

In writing this piece, I followed certain fundamental guidelines or basic principles of essay writing including by first establishing thesis key thematic issues from the reading materials that I was going to write on (EUCLID 2019, 1). I further conducted research on the proposed topics from varied sources including books, internet, and conversation with my peers. In each of these information gathering process, I duly took note and seek for clarification from others including your truly – Dr. Kabiru, the course instructor.

3) ACCURACY, CONCISENESS, AND CLARITY

The concept of accuracy, conciseness, and clarity is part of my day to day administrative functions. Partly because American society and particularly “folks” at the Department of State have been inundated with reports from around the world. They practically do not have the time to read elaborate essays. Therefore, they encourage drafters to make their essays and other reports brief, clear, accurate, and unambiguous. From the reading materials I have been privy to, I noticed that Euclid University seems comfortable with concise and accurate reporting of information that contains only the data relevant to the readership and record-keeping process.

During the drafting process of this essay, I asked myself how would I ensure that this draft fulfills this requirement? The answer to this is by having a thorough knowledge of the subject matter. With the desire to draft accurate, concise, and clear essays, I read through relevant slides and learning materials that were available in the LMS system. I further made a special effort to even consult other related materials with the view of drafting an unambiguous essay. The knowledge acquired through those readings informed my judgment that an essay is a concise and accurate record of information that contains only the data relevant to the readership and record. An essay should be neatly laid out and easy to read with a simple structure that allows easy access to the information code on the information (EUCLID 2019, 2).

4) REFERENCING DILEMMA

Before my exposure to the ACA 401 - Turabian, Zotero, and chrome connector as instruments to do citations and referencing, I was very comfortable with the usual word generated manual input of citations. It is not only pitiable for me but its more than laughable as well for me to have done so by referencing and citations crudely and manually. Following my exposure to better and modern styles of referencing, I will henceforth use Zotero and Chrome connector to do my in-text citations, footnote, and endnote citations and referencing when writing briefings, articles, and other academic papers. The ACA-401 recommends the Turabian style of referencing which seems quite fascinating to me. Even now, I still considered this to be learning by doing exercise until I perfect it.

In addition to the above, the Turabian in-text citation does not only enable me to locate sources of information, but it also enables me to give credit to persons and individuals for their creative and intellectual works I have utilized in the process of drafting this essay. Furthermore, the University of Pittsburgh explained that citations and referencing do not only locate particular sources of information, rather it combats plagiarism (<https://pitt.libguides.com/citationhelp>).

The ACA-401 coursepack further explained the academic discipline that is suitable for the use of the respective referencing styles such as the American Psychological Association (APA), the Modern Language Association (MLA), and the Chicago/Turabian styles. Moreover, the question of what citation to adopt remains largely problematic, especially when there are multiple citations and referencing styles. One perfect solution I discovered from reading the ACA-401 learning materials is that citation style largely depends on the academic discipline involved and a matter of choice for institutions and instructors. For instance, the Turabian style In-Text (Parenthetical) citations and reference list are the recommended styles by the EUCLID University, especially for the social sciences and humanity schools (EUCLID 2019, 46).

5) QUOTING, PARAPHRASING, AND SUMMARIZING

Whether in an academic environment or a professional setting, quoting, paraphrasing, and summarizing are generally acceptable. It is a rule of thumb that sources of information must be referenced to ensure legitimacy, reliability, and credibility within the department of State. Similarly so, from the ACA-401 coursepack, EUCLID's strongly recommends that students act in fairness to themselves, their instructors, and the scientific community by quoting a piece of work that is not originally theirs. For the ACA-401 coursepack, quotations must match the source document word for word and must be attributed to the original author (EUCLID 2019, 46). Paraphrasing, on the other hand, involves putting a passage from source material into your own words ((EUCLID 2019, 46).13). A paraphrase must also be attributed to the source and in most cases shorter than the original passage, taking a somewhat broader segment of the source and condensing it slightly. As opposed to quoting and paraphrasing, putting the main idea(s) into your own words is the definition of summary.

While some students find it hard to get their thoughts and ideas down on paper, most others do not know how to properly incorporate quotations into sentences. As a result of this lack of knowledge to either summarize or paraphrase, copying from one source and pasting it into another is often the only option students have exploited whilst trying to meet their respective academic requirements, thus leading to academic fraud otherwise known as plagiarism.

6) PLAGIARISM

Not until I learned about a controversy around a well-respected intellectual in Sierra Leone being reprimanded by the University of Pretoria – South Africa for plagiarism conduct. The University of Pretoria even threatened to withhold his Ph.D., which they conferred on the person in question for intellectual dishonesty. Thereafter I took my time trying to understand the elements of plagiarism for the first time. I understand plagiarism as the use of the exact words or ideas taken from a resource without clearly quoting or acknowledging that source (Mackenzie 2007, 49). According to the ACA-401 coursepack, when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information commits an act of plagiarism.”, (EUCLID 2019, 5). Warning students against plagiarism, the ACA-401 coursepack view that plagiarism is an unfair, unethical, and a serious academic offense that is tantamount serious repercussion (EUCLID 2019, 5).

So, when EUCLID University’s ACA-401 coursepack presents me with the opportunity to read with a commitment to understanding academic writing and the essence of referencing people for their creativity, I understand why the EUCLID University frowns at plagiarism. As a result, the ACA-401 course recommends that students take careful notes on every source including books, interviews, television shows, websites, etc. which we might use in our writings. Among other things, studies have indicated some of the causative factors or reasons for plagiarism among students include "... academic procrastination, the desire to have a better grade, fear of failing, and in most cases their confusion about what constitutes plagiarism," (Pecorari 2008, 12). Given what I have studied from the ACA-401 coursepack on what constitutes plagiarism? Causes of plagiarism, and the motivating factors of plagiarism, the ACA-401 coursepack argued that one way a student may avoid plagiarism is to always put quotation marks around words that s/he copies exactly and state the source of information by referencing that source. However, one does not need to use quotation marks if the sentence or expression is tampered with, including changing the original structure of the sentence (Oshima & Hogue 2006, 52).

7) CONCLUSION

All over the world, academic writing including research papers, theses, and dissertations is a Herculean task for not only non-English speakers but also for English

speakers. Considering the complexity and challenges associated with academic writing including formatting and citation styles, punctuation and grammar, adherence to intellectual property regulations, lexical difficulties, and methodologies used in data collections, the world has witnessed an unprecedented decline of authors.

Before the emergence of technology which has made it less difficult for students and instructors to properly format academic writings, the academic community encountered a serious referencing dilemma. This dilemma has often resulted in the use of the exact words taken from a resource without clearly quoting or acknowledging that source, resulting in academic fraud and cheating.

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